

DETERMINANTS OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF SMALL AND MICRO COMMUNITY ENTERPRISE OF HERBAL PRODUCTS IN THAILAND

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Abstract

The competitive advantage and effectiveness of the organization are considered to be important factors of the organization that could help to any organizations for the survival of long term. If the organization could not be able to achieve their competitive advantage and effectiveness on other organizations or products. Then their share in the market could be decreased. Therefore, the competitive advantage (COA) and effectiveness (EFF) could be considered important factors. There are various factors that could effect to competitive advantage and effectiveness. Among of those factors, human resource management (HRM), innovation management (INM), quality management (QUM) are important factors that could increase the organization competitive advantage and effectiveness. To address this issue, the current study objective was established to investigate the effect of HRM, INM, and QUM on COA and EFF of small and micro community enterprise of herbal products in Thailand. For this objective, the data was collected from the employees of small and micro community enterprises of productions in Thailand by using a convenient sampling technique. The Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique had shown that all of predictors (human resources management, innovation management, and quality management) had a positive and significant relationship with the competitive advantage and effectiveness. Therefore, these findings could contribute a body of literature in the extant literature to increase the future research.

Keywords: Competitive advantage, effectiveness herbal business, Thailand

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary environment, the competitive advantage of any company played an important role in the development of economic development of any country. The competitive advantage of the organizations could improve along with various indicators. Among of those indicators, human resource management (HRM), innovation management (INM), and quality management (QUM) are considered to be important indicators to increase the competitive advantage (COA) and effectiveness (EFF) of the business, (Progoulaki & Theotokas, 2010; Powell, 1995; Dereli, 2015). Therefore, it is argued in the extant literature that contribution to national economic development, innovation is all important elements for businesses as they deal with global competition.

Few empirical studies find a link between high QUM and CA (KLER et al., 2016; McCage et al., 2002). Two contrasting viewpoints can be found in the literature: One theory suggests that successful QUM will need to be applied comprehensively in order to generate COA, while another theory maintains that because only some quality management are positively

related with COA(Gowen & Tallon, 2003; Ouarghidi, Powell, Martin, De Boer, & Abbad, 2012). Although it has been found that these two variables have a direct correlation, it appears that their nature remains unclear; thus, competitive advantage may be derived from a combination of these two practices.

Along with the QOA, management focuses on the significance of companies' HRM in a manner that contributes to long-term sustainable COA(Cecilia, Al Washali, Albishty, Suriani, & Rosliza, 2017). Today, it is widely believed that a company's success is reliant on the proper management of its HRM, which in turn presents a monetary and COA. Due to their relatively low wages, limited training, and dedication to the goals of the firm, crews can help the company save money on ship maintenance or avoid the need to hire additional people.

In addition to QOA and HRM, the researchers conducted in the 1990s, 2000s, and earlier this decade has found that INM influences a business's financial performance (Deshpande & Bhalsing, 2013; Harrison, Holt, Pattison, & Elton, 2004; Kiesow & Hurley, 1995; Parsaei et al., 2016). INM is critically important when it comes to setting business strategy. As well, there have been numerous prior studies conducted in various firms on the topic of innovation, examining the subject of products and processes (Bahmani, Tajeddini, et al., 2016). While the services sector has increased to play a massive role in the modern economy (Y.-T. Lin et al., 2017; Oldenboom & Abratt, 2000), service-related empirical research appears to be rather lacking (Jansen et al., 2000). Although our understanding of the relationship between innovation and businesses such as restaurants, hotels, and leisure companies is limited, it would be more accurate to say that we have no knowledge about the effect of innovation on these types of companies (Bahmani, Baharvand-Ahmadi, Tajeddini, Rafieian-Kopaei, & Naghdi, 2016).

In addition to effect of INM, HRM and QUM on COA. Previous studied also found that these indicators had also significant effect on EFF. For instance, QUM had positive effect on EFF(Cude, 2001; Kull & Wacker, 2010). On the other hand, HRM had also a significant relationship with the EFF(Ferris et al., 1998; Richard & Johnson, 2001). In addition, INM had also a significant relation with the effectiveness (AlHarrasi, 2016). These findings had shown that all of these indicators are important indicators for the EFF.

Along with significance of predictors, various studies still had some gaps. Firstly the previous studies still had some inconsistent findings. Secondly, previous studies had a direct effect on effeteness while did not had indirect effect on EFF. Thirdly, previous studies mostly had the individual effect of HRM, INM, and QUM on COA and EFF. While previous studies had a little attention on the combined effect of HRM, INM, QUM on COA and EFF. In addition, previous studies had a major focus on developed countries while had a little attention on developing countries especially Thailand Small and Micro Community Enterprise of Herbal Products. This sector in Thailand played an important role in the economic and social development of Thailand. Therefore, this sector could not be ignored. Based on previous gaps the current study purpose is to investigate the effect of HRM, INM, QUM on COA and EFF of Small and Micro Community Enterprise of Herbal Products in Thailand.

Literature Review

Quality Management, Competitive advantage and Effectiveness

In line with the RBV theory, several academics mentioned the possibility of utilizing a strategy based on quality management, which brings together a variety of complementary practices intended to increase the business's productivity and revenue (Anderson, Rungtusanatham, & Schroeder, 1994; Seawright & Young, 1996). Flynn, Schroeder, and Sakakibara (1994) noted, for example, that while competitors are able to copy quality management practices, because the practices continually improve, quality management is "always a moving target" (p. 344). Following an excellent theoretical analysis of the strategic potential of TQM, Powell (1995) argued that, when viewed from the perspective of a resource-based business, TQM may be difficult to implement in its entirety. In fact, according to Mr. Burke, TQM is plagued by lack of standardization, the absence of connectedness of resources, open-endedness in which goals are unknown and ambiguous relationships and relationships between tasks. An additional explanation of quality management is that it can help companies reach their desired results despite the possibility of differences in business results, since this quality management can be transferred to other firms.

Reed, Lemak, and Mero (2000) asserted that complex and intricate implementation processes are harder to mimic because of that. In other words, Escrig-Tena (2004) proposes that, because of effective application of quality management principles, organizations can cultivate distinct cross-functional competencies that, if further developed, could lead to increased productivity and increased revenue. Quality management as a management capability is therefore not extremely common since the presence of quality management on its own doesn't guarantee that a business will thrive; rather, a business's quality management effectiveness must be better than that of its competitors in order to be successful (Yang, Wong, & Liao, 2021). Theories involving quality management practices being tested include those that examine their direct effects on a firm's competitive advantage.

According to quality management (QUM) literature, top management leadership is important in establishing an overall environment and heading in the right direction for continuous improvement (Ebrahimi & Sadeghi, 2013; Phan, Abdallah, & Matsui, 2011). Executives have a leadership role in the process of getting quality management systems implemented and driving better business performance (Tari, Molina, & Castejon, 2007). Leadership ability that cannot be duplicated may provide a source of competitive advantage (Pobkeeree, Sawanpanyalert, & Sirichotiratana, 2010; Tontini & Bento, 2020). An in-depth review of some empirical studies shows this to be true. For instance, a survey of manufacturing and service firms with over 50 employees found that the TQM-using firms demonstrated that leadership was in the form of tacit behavior, as well as behavioral and inimitable features of quality management. Top management commitment/leadership was also found to be associated with competitive advantage by El Shenawy, Baker, and Lemak (2007), who found that this concept fit into their meta-analysis of 51 studies.

It's not only that quality management practices are intended to improve the effectiveness of the product, but they are also implemented in order to fulfil customers' needs and make the product error-free, such as by eliminating rework (Linderman, Schroeder, Zaheer, Liedtke, & Choo, 2004). The quality of a product is defined by manufacturing resources that are oriented towards producing competitive advantage and low defects (Ahire & Dreyfus, 2000). These are QM practices to better position the manufacturing workforce so they can focus on quality by implementing things like more standardized processes (e.g. SPC), better documentation (e.g. ISO 9000), more cooperation and collaboration (e.g. TQM), and deeper advancement (aka A change in strategy for what to accomplish) (e.g. six-sigma). Quality management practices are found to increase the quality and overall performance of products in empirical studies (Nair, 2006; Naveh & Erez, 2004; Salvador, Forza, Rungtusanatham, & Choi, 2001; Zhang, Linderman, & Schroeder, 2012). The results of this study explore the connection between quality practices and quality performance. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1: QUM had a significant relationship with HRM.

H2: QUM management had a significant relationship with effectiveness.

Innovation Management, competitive advantage and Effectiveness

The implementation of organizational innovations takes place through managerial activities, which follow a defined process with irregular and complex structures to help the company adapt to changing internal and external environments. When we use the term "innovation," we mean "process," but when we use it as innovation management, we mean the control and management of innovation (Dereli, 2015). While a company's competitive advantage describes the advantages that a company has over its competitors, creating better value for customers is known as a company's competitive advantage. Reaching price and quality advantages, as well as responding quickly to customer needs, are just a few of the numerous ways of generating competitive advantage. The most direct way to discover new market opportunities and discover new products and services is to use innovation. The proper and efficient management of the process from the inception of innovation to commercialization and marketing is essential in order to achieve this objective. For this purpose, the strategies need to be implemented according to a plan and kept up to date as needed. Porter's research found that there are specific strategies that companies can follow to achieve a competitive advantage in global competition. First, all organizations' value systems must be dealt with. Otherwise, the resources must be continuously developed and preserved resources, ongoing research, innovation, and transformation must be sustainable. Global strategies must be formulated and implemented in order to maintain a competitive advantage (Dereli, 2015; Kerdpitak, 2022). To succeed in innovation, high-level management support and attachment are necessary. Most particularly, in cases where innovation results in sweeping alterations, leadership calls for aggressive, costly learning and change. It is also a critical variable to consider when evaluating the performance of innovation. In order to keep a productive, satisfied, talented, and successful workforce, businesses must strive to maintain a top-notch work environment that meets the employees' needs, nourishes their talents, and supports their careers. Innovative behaviors should be supported through empowerment and involvement

practices. Additionally, through the use of cross-functional teamwork, the various viewpoints can be combined and new ideas can be sparked. Showing the ability to identify new information and knowledge, as well as to apply it, indicates an organization's ability to discover and provide innovative output creative (Prajogo & Ahmed, 2006). In the current business environment, customers are faced with time-based competition, where customers who are growing increasingly impatient favor providers who provide quality services brought on time (Kasemsap, 2017). In order to remain competitive in the current business environment, it is imperative that businesses constantly provide improved products to consumers (Day & Wensley, 1988). Quality function deployment (C. Lin, Chow, Madu, Kuei, & Yu, 2005; Tajeddini, 2011), increased market and learning orientation Tajeddini (2009), and upgraded technology are cited as significant contributing factors to improving overall quality. Internal control evaluation encompasses evaluating whether the control system is operating as designed (Bolívar-Ramos, Garcia-Morales, & García-Sánchez, 2012). To paraphrase Miller, Spann, and Lerner (1991), a company's "core competencies" are its "capabilities and competencies," which must interact to implement the overall strategy. This means that to some extent, the possible strategies that a company can implement in the short term are determined by the skill sets required to implement them (Miller et al., 1991). To attain high-quality results, companies must design technologies that can produce and deliver products and processes that meet customers' and customers' expectations and develop a company-wide customer-focused quality culture. According to Fang, Ma, Ren, and Zhou (2014), investors may be taking risks in order to provide long-term strategic flexibility. Thus, the chance of operational effectiveness is also secured. While all of these reasons above point to the need for creative and innovative organizations to be ahead of customers' wants and needs, it is accepted that innovative organizations will have a higher OE because of the higher quality and greater competitive advantage. Firms' offerings will be perceived as of premium quality in return (Chang, 2011). Competitive advantage and operational effectiveness both benefit from this view of the world. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H3: INM had a significant relationship with HRM.

H4: INM had a significant relationship with effectiveness.

Human resource management, competitive advantage and Effectiveness

According to Saha and Gregar (2012), HRM is viewed as a structure of human resources in which a firm uses it, as well as other activities that are aimed at advancing the organization's goals. A concept the organizers of this event mention is that of a strategic HRM in which a company's ability to influence its performance is dependent on the management of its human resources and where other activities are used to create a system, instead of being viewed as a single entity. Although this theory has been criticized, studies have found a clear connection between human resources and organizational performance. There is an increase in studies in support of the strong correlation. In the literature, various methods have been employed to gauge HRM, for instance, those that utilize HR-orientation, work-life balance, and individual HR factors (Datta, Guthrie, & Wright, 2005; Delery, 1998). Nonetheless, business firms have become increasingly engaged in searching for sustainable competitive advantages because of

the substantial influence of technological advancement, globalization, and other forces (B. Obeidat, Tawalbeh, & Akour, 2019).

There are 35 total factors. Meanwhile, plenty of literature on sustainability is available, especially on competitive advantage determinants. It was observed that for some authors, critical factors include dynamic capabilities, such as innovation (Carmona-Moreno, Céspedes-Lorente, & Martínez-del-Río, 2012; D. Obeidat, Yousef, Tawalbeh, & Masa'deh, 2018), intellectual capital, such as human capital (Gilani, Zadeh, & Sadari, 2012), and entrepreneurial skills (Hamadamin & Atan, 2019). Although both groups agreed that short-term advantages may fade over time, Atteya (2012) and Wiggins and Ruefli (2002) concluded that they do not believe long-term competitive advantages are sustainable. Conversely, S. W. Ahmed and Siddiqui (2020) postulated that thinking about the sustainability of short-term advantages is destructive." Other authors contend that for an organization to secure long-term competitive advantages, it is necessary for these firms to systematically cultivate their human resources in order to have the capacity to utilize their tacit knowledge for competitive advantage. Employee management systems impact a company's ability to create a sustainable competitive advantage by doing the following: Since the introduction of new strategic concepts and management, the firm's position in the market has allowed room for them to act strategically in order to do well in the market. The following will prompt firms to focus on how they can use human resources and quality management to achieve a competitive advantage. Previous research has dealt with aspects of HRM functions, and previous research suggests that HRM is dependent on the organization's strategy for SCA. Direct correlation between HRM bundles and sustainable competitive advantage must be investigated...

In the modern era, businesses have to deal with completely different trends, such as product and technological change that is occurring at an increasing rate, intense international competition, deregulation, a demographic shift, and a shift towards a service society. Every industry has experienced a dramatic increase in competition due to these industry trends. To do well in such an environment, a company must become a highly effective competitor or cease to exist (Hashim & Hameed, 2012). Human resource management practices have gained importance in a competitive work environment like this. Workforce studies have shown a link between increased productivity, excellent customer service, better profitability, and overall organizational survival (Delery, 1998; Stavrou & Brewster, 2005) and (Welbourne & Andrews, 1996). When it comes to the implementation of such a link, the company must not only deal with the current issues associated with human resource management but also anticipate and respond to future issues regarding human resource management. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H5: Competitive advantage had a significant relationship with HRM.

H6: Competitive advantage had also a positive and significant association with effectiveness.

H7: HRM had a significant relationship with effectiveness.

The above discussion had become of research framework that is presented below.

Figure.1: Research Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A correlational research is when two or more things have connection between. The correlational research approach is used to investigate the impact of human resource management (HRM), innovation management (INM), quality management (QU) on competitive advantage (COA) and effectiveness (EFF) of small and micro community enterprise of herbal products in Thailand. Moreover, the study used the cross sectional research design. The target population for this study is the employees of small and micro community enterprise of herbal products in Thailand. The data collection technique was used in this study was self-administered questionnaire. The sampling technique in this study is the non-probability convenience sampling. This technique has been used to easily contact and reach the respondents to get the responses. This technique is cost and time effective as well as the data is conveniently available. All the study constructs are used in this study adapted from the previous studies to achieve the study objective.

1. Analysis and results

The data was analyzed on following two steps. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was done by using SPSS software while inferential statistics was done by using an AMOS. When the process of data collection is finished, the final questionnaires are chosen for the further preliminary analysis. Due to preliminary data analysis, statistical errors were avoided as a precondition for data analysis in the first phase. This preliminary analysis involves normality checks, missing value evaluations, outlier's checks and common method variance tests of the system. However, some missing values were found and solved using the most suggested mean replacement method. This mean replacement method has been widely anticipated by the researchers as the most effective tool for social science studies (Hair, Matthews, Matthews, & Sarstedt, 2017). This approach also does not effect from removing or altering other sample entries, for example lists of

elimination and pair-wise deletion, nor from adjusting the mean values of the other variables (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014).

Descriptive Statistics

SPSS developed descriptive analyses. The Tables.1 presents the results of the descriptive analysis. Based on the analysis, it appears that the respondent's view of the variables matches their beliefs. All of the item's mean scores were included in the analysis. On the whole, the average scores of all the variables lie between 3.51 and 4.25. Since respondents are so heavily involved in the independent and dependent variables activities, therefore the mean scores are highly moderated. Also, the standard deviation of all of the variables was all situated from 0.71 to 0.77. The mean score and standard deviation of all the variables are depicted in the following Table.1.

Table 1 Statistical test of empirical variables

Variable	Range	Min	Max	\bar{x}	SD.	Variance	Sk	Ku
Quality Management								
QU1	3.33	1.67	5.00	4.21	0.73	0.55	-0.94	0.57
QU2	3.75	1.50	5.00	4.20	0.72	0.51	-0.99	1.05
QU3	3.50	1.50	5.00	4.11	0.75	0.53	-0.98	0.79
Innovative Management								
IM1	3.00	2.00	5.00	3.87	0.75	0.55	0.53	-0.59
IM2	3.20	1.85	5.00	3.85	0.76	0.57	-0.35	-0.53
IM3	3.00	2.00	5.00	3.73	0.76	0.56	0.34	-0.62
Competitive Advantage □□□□□□□□								
CA1	3.30	2.00	5.00	4.19	0.79	0.65	-0.83	0.43
CA2	3.10	1.98	5.00	4.15	0.78	0.62	-0.75	0.53
CA3	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.17	0.76	0.55	-0.77	0.39
Human Resource Management								
HR1	3.60	1.40	5.00	3.99	0.79	0.68	-0.69	-0.37
HR2	3.55	1.25	5.00	4.15	0.75	0.62	-0.75	0.28
HR3	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.10	0.76	0.64	-0.72	-0.46
HR4	3.80	2.00	5.00	4.19	0.73	0.57	-0.73	-0.53
HR5	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.20	0.72	0.55	-0.76	-0.44
Effectiveness								
FF1	3.50	1.50	5.00	4.16	0.76	0.68	-0.97	0.42
EF2	3.85	1.50	5.00	4.15	0.78	0.69	-1.00	0.51
EF3	3.10	2.00	5.00	4.08	0.77	0.61	0.35	-0.63

Note: COA-competitive advantage, QUM-quality management, HRM-human resource management, EFF-effeteness, INM-innovation management.

1.1.Measurement model

This research used the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to examine the model of this study as suggested by the previous researchers (N. Ahmad, Ahmad, & Zakaria, 2019; R. Ahmad, Ahmad, Farhan, & Arshad, 2020; R. Ahmad, Bin Mohammad, & Nordin, 2019; R. AHMED, RIAZ, AQDAS, & HASSAN, 2021; Bhatti, Farhan, Ahmad, & Sharif, 2019; Zakaria, Ahmad, & Ahmad, 2020). “Measurement model assesses the, internal consistency reliability, Cronbach alpha (CA), composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted AVE.”As seen in Table 2, all outer loads of individual items are greater than the value of 0.70. The minimum threshold of 0.70 is also reached by composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values, which indicates that all the tests are stable in terms of their individual item reliability and composite reliability (Wong, 2013). In addition, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values above the threshold value of 0.50 for each construct indicated statistical correctness for all objects in the measurement model.

Table 2 Factor Loadings. (n = 340)

Variable	λ	SE.	t-value	R ²	AVE	CR.
Quality Management					0.799	0.915
QU1 (Parameter constants)	0.84	-	-	0.81		
QU2	0.71	0.061	16.443**	0.68		
QU3	0.94	0.052	21.234**	0.79		
Innovative Management					0.842	0.901
IM1(Parameter constants)	0.90	-	-	0.83		
IM2	0.94	0.073	14.535**	0.79		
IM3	0.92	0.066	15.733**	0.81		
Competitive Advantage					0.946	0.974
CA1 (Parameter constants)	0.89	-	-	0.89		
CA2	0.98	0.050	17.228**	0.82		
CA3	0.98	0.06	20.211**	0.78		
Human Resource Management					0.927	0.957
HR1 (Parameter constants)	0.94	-	-	0.87		
HR2	0.95	0.068	24.453**	0.89		
HR3	0.97	0.053	21.813**	0.63		
HR4	0.99	0.040	19.651**	0.77		
HR5	0.99	0.041	22.176**	0.81		
Effectiveness					0.901	0.923
EF1 (Parameter constants)	0.88	-	-	0.91		
EF2	0.98	0.070	23.842**	0.88		
EF 3	0.92	0.051	14.791**	0.81		

Note: COA-competitive advantage, QUM-quality management, HRM-human resource management, EFF-effeteness, INM-innovation management.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Note: COA-competitive advantage, QUM-quality management, HRM-human resource management, EFF-effeteness, INM-innovation management.

1.2.Structural Model

The main results of the analysis showed that quality management had a positive and meaningful competitive advantage correlation which validated for the proposed hypothesis. Furthermore, the findings also indicate that innovative management has also a positive and important relation with competitive advantage as that supports to proposed hypothesis. In addition, the human resource management also has a strong and important correlation with competitive advantage and supports to the proposed hypothesis. On the other hand, the quality management had also a positive and significant relationship with the effectives that supports to the proposed hypothesis. The key findings had also indicated that innovative management has also a positive and significant relation with effectiveness as that supports to proposed hypothesis. In addition, the human resource management also has a strong and important correlation with effectiveness and supports to the proposed hypothesis. The above direct effect findings had shown that the entire proposed hypothesis of the study had been accepted which shows that when quality management, innovation management, human resource management are increased then the competitive advantage and effectiveness are also increased. Therefore, these indicators are considered to be important predictors to increase the competitive advantage and effectiveness. All of the results are predicted in the following Table.3 below.

Table3 Results of hypotheses testing

Variable			λ	SE.	t-value	Sig.	R ²
HRM	<--	QUM	0.59	0.08	7.011	0.000**	0.71
HRM	<--	INM	0.57	0.09	5.872	0.000**	0.71
HRM	<--	COA	0.49	0.08	5.165	0.000**	0.71
EFF	<--	QUM	0.61	0.10	3.436	0.001*	0.76
EFF	<--	INM	0.55	0.07	2.782	0.008*	0.76
EFF	<--	COA	0.61	0.21	2.832	0.003*	0.76
EFF	<--	HRM	0.65	0.13	3.876	0.000**	0.76

Note: COA-competitive advantage, QUM-quality management, HRM-human resource management, EFF-effeteness, INM-innovation management.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The competitive advantage and effectiveness of the organization are considered to be important factors of the organization that could help to any organizations for the survival of long term. If the organization could not be able to achieve their competitive advantage and effectiveness on other organizations or products. Then their share in the market could be decreased. Therefore, the competitive advantage and effectiveness could be considered important factors. There are various factors that could effect to competitive advantage and effectiveness. Among of those factors, human resource management (HRM), innovation management (INM), quality management (QUM) are important factors that could increase the organization competitive advantage (CA) and effectiveness (EFF). To address this issue, the current study objective was established to investigate the effect of HRM, INM, and QUM on COA and EFF of small and micro community enterprise of herbal products in Thailand. For this objective, the data was collected from the employees of small and micro community enterprises of productions in Thailand through convenient sampling method. The Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) method had shown that all of predictors had a positive and significant relationship that supports to the entire proposed hypothesis. These findings are further in line with previous studies who had also found the same results (Beckmerhagen, Berg, Karapetrovic, & Willborn, 2004; Chan, Shaffer, & Snape, 2004; Elshaer & Augustyn, 2016; Gyemang & Emeagwali, 2020; Kerdpitak & Jermisittiparsert, 2020; Khatri, 2000; Kull & Wacker, 2010; Powell, 1995; Prescott, 2016). These findings had shown that QUM, INM, and HRM are important factor for the COA and EFF of the organizations. Therefore, it could be concluded that small enterprises of the Thailand had greater level of quality management system in their organizations to increase their competitive advantage. As, all of the hypothesis of the study are supported. Therefore, this study added a body of literature that could contribute in the extant literature. Firstly, this study could help to the researchers to increase their research in future. Secondly, this model is considered to be unique in the extant literature, therefore this study could contribute a good findings in the extant literature. Thirdly this study could also help to the policy makers and managers to know about the

importance of human resource management, innovation management, and quality management to increase their organization competitive advantage.

Limitations and recommendations

There various limitations of the study that could become a new area of research in future. The study was limited on Thailand that is a developing country which findings could not be generalized on other developed countries. Therefore a future study could be done other developed countries to increase research generalizability. Moreover, a future study could be done along with the moderating variable that could increase the predictive relevance of the model. In other words, a future research could establish on longitudinal to increase the research generalizability because this study had a limitation of cross sectional research design.

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